

The Importance of Self Economic Management in School

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Abstract

The current study addressed self-management in schools and how it is applied through discussing the concept of school management, school management styles which consists of three sections, namely the Central Administration and the decentralized management, a style combining centralized and decentralized administrations, and the concept of self-management in schools, and also addressed the importance of self-management for the school since it contributes to involving parents and important people. The benefits of self-management of the school stems from the system of self-management in schools that seeks in particular to achieve educational reform within the State.

Keywords: Self-Management in Schools, Decision- Making, Administrative Decentralization.

Introduction

Education still obtains an important aspect of care and attention, it includes several elements: the teacher, the student and the school curriculum, teaching methods and teaching in school, but evolution, which contained all the items and tools must contain educational administration in particular.

Self-management is the Executive Management for educational policies, whose main task is to create a suitable climate for school staff, faculty or administrators, and others, to achieve the desired progress and considering that the management of the school is the only way to understand the decisions associated with the domain, in addition to being the sole delegate of implementation, it is important then to work on the development of strategic management in order to be effective and active in decision-making, since it directly relates to the conditions and positions related to education and has the capacity, If developed, to solve problems that occur in the educational process for the advancement and development of school management. School management has emerged recently in some Arabic countries such as Egypt, Qatar and Oman, in Egypt it is called (school decentralization), in Qatar, called (independent schools), in the Sultanate of Oman it was called (subjective schools).

Self-management in schools is an Executive gateway, allowing autonomy at school, and measures the ability of the school to open in general society, but was later linked with many other government institutions and non-governmental organizations, where it received the attention of the majority of intellectuals, where its contribution is effective especially in the non-Arabic educational system, so we must embrace this trend in Arabic educational systems, it concentrated mainly on making school's attention focused on the Department as an Administrative unit, since work in the school is done through the principle of decentralization in some operations and administrative functions, and at the same time, its responsibilities for evaluation process internally and externally, through the participation of employed persons in administrative work, and decision-making, resulting in what could be called accountability, to guide the work properly and to proper terms, in addition to the participation of those who are involved in the community as the foreign sectors in the outline of the educational process, this helps to achieve a sense of responsibility by all those affected and influenced by education.[4]

The scholastic administration school administration is defined as a set of systematic efforts by a group of employees within it to achieve specific goals in accordance with the policies of the school that are set to the breeding of students on sound principles. [3]

The Patterns of Educational Administration

The regulation in education and the diversity of functions and levels of the educational management patterns, there are three types of school administration are as follows: [3]

- i) The firm centralized administration pattern: this is the firm pattern through the herarchical serial administrations that is divided to multiple administrative stages, where each measurement is provided to suit the educational policies to reach the lowest administrative stage in total commitment with all it involves as instructions, orders, decisions, and organizations.
- ii) Decentralized management pattern: a pattern that reflects the overall style of the Central Administration and dissimilar, where in this style the departments operate separately and independently from the central Department.
- iii) The pattern of combining centralized and decentralized administrations on achieving the partnership on supervision and execution.

Self Management Concept

[The process of redistribution of power to degrade the power of governing schools educational authorities, based its message on local control, and its own affairs and build improvement strategies, and change organizational arrangements in the structure of the school, the collective participation of teachers, parents, and community members in educational decision-making at the school level]. [6]

It is a method that is followed by the school administration for drafting school functions, depending on the circumstances, characteristics and needs, so the members of the School Board be more independent and responsible in investing the possibilities for the solution of some problems and activate educational events for school development in the long term. [9]

[It is a useful mechanism for development and educational change and increase of the effectiveness of school-level work due to the authorities and school administration broad powers to limit the centralism and ensure the implementation of the quality circles and success in school]. [8]

[Contemporary management portal based on the school as a separate administrative unit, have a discretion in the management of their own affairs through a move towards greater decentralization in the various areas of work, with the school for an effective system of accountability through the provision of quality educational outcomes]. [1]

The Significance of Self-Management

self-management contributes in involving parents and influential persons in addition to the community school personnel, who are responsible for enacting the necessary decisions which are in the interest of the pupil, where high power is delegated certain tasks to other aspects, in order to apply them effectively in decision-making on educational issues within the school, accompanied by practical use of democracy and a sense of trust, where the self-management importance lies in the following points:

Participation with communities in decision-making on educational matters by people interested in education within the school to their sense of ownership, and therefore their cooperation is sincere and serious to accept full consent to implement decisions.

Self-management works in school to promote invention and innovation in response to the needs of students in the school and organize some useful programs for them.

Self-management supports confidence of parents in practice within the school, especially as it offers the opportunity for all those interested to have an idea of the costs of programs and activities and their funding sources and the amount of spending limits. [9]

Benefits of Self-Management

The system of self-management in schools seeks in particular to achieve educational reform within the State through achieving high flexibility and necessary for the involvement of various parties concerned, to determine the different needs and requirements of the students that vary from one environment to other and strive towards them .

Self-management in schools and in business proved successful, where it worked on transferring decision-making authority to lower levels either in school or elsewhere, thereby increasing the sense of the staff job satisfaction, so that they have the power to effectively influence the way the performance of their functions and organizational duties, increases their sense of job satisfaction, employee involvement in decision-making is working on creating a sense of owning the thing

and joining the organization so the pursuit of proficiency and work to verify the desired objectives in time and thereby contribute to the creation of individuals with self-autonomous supervision. [5]

Self-management within the school contribute to the improvement of education through increasing the amount that is used in the educational process and an increase in school subjects in proportion to satisfy the needs of the local community in addition to the increase of options and opportunities for students to choose the style of education that corresponds to their nature, which contribute to the output of education. Self-management also operates to reduce bribery and embezzlement and moral corruption of certain individuals at the international level by reducing financial bureaucracy. [7]

Self-management characteristics

The self-management in schools seeks to meet the needs of students and the local community, led by relevant parties to input in the decision-making process, making education distinct and different from the rest of regular schools, as well as introducing some changes to the school-related tasks, and management strategies, resources and supervision and evaluation and other operations, some of the important features of the school's administration are as follows: [5]

- i) Self management concentrates on the organizational culture within the school which in turn affects the tasks related to the educational process and thus on school performance.
- ii) Schools work on the educational process in accordance with their characteristics and demands.
- iii) Self-management works to promote, strengthen and consolidate the innovative thought in solving problems.
- iv) There is multiple methods of school management in self-managed schools, according to the plurality of human nature.
- v) The objectives of the self-managed schools vary and could be more precise to meet the needs of the future. [5]

Scholastic Self-Management Objectives

Self-management is working to establish specific targets to be achieved, and self-management as a process, its primary objective it pursues is to ensure the participation of teachers, parents, community members and businessmen in decision making in an effort to improve the conditions of education.

The primary goal of self-management is the shift from centralized to decentralized through the opportunity for students, teachers and Director of various decisions such as curriculum reform and control of available resources according to their needs, and there are some things that are related to the educational process in order to achieve efficiency and removing obstacles and achieving flexibility, efficiency and productivity in addition to better identify appropriate programmes for demand and to motivate them to participate in operations.

An important objective of decentralization in education lies in improving the quality of education, and also assessing the services and indicatives of high quality, diverse and optimum allocation of human and material resources and employ it constantly rallied quickly in the work plus the necessary renovations to the educational process so that Governments possess much of the information that works to help realize steps concerning the educational innovation faster and better, in addition to increased administrative competencies within the Ministry of education.[9]

Financial Self Management

Most decentralization strategies, whether openly or not, seek to transfer some degree of financial responsibility for education to regional and/or municipal governments or the private sector. Assuming that resource mobilization capacity exists at lower levels [for example, through taxing authority or privatization plans], a reasonable degree of responsibility for financial decentralization can be healthy for the development of education. Quite simply, when regional and local governments are investing their own resources, they tend to take greater care in how the money is spent. [4,]

Governments use various approaches to decentralize financial responsibility:

- i) Transfer responsibility to the provinces.
- ii) Growth in the educational system, such as hiring more teachers, financing new construction, or buying more instructional equipment.
- iii) Block grant approach: Each autonomous community could select and pursue its own priorities—for example, health, education, or transportation— using funds generated regionally and nationally.
- iv) Educational privatization: Privatization can operate in two directions: the use of private sector funds to support public schools, or the use of public funds to support private schools.

researchers and intellectuals called for giving full authority to act in the school budget and what it may consider appropriate to the needs of the students and the community, and to give each school appropriately net amount.

Financial need for all schools was decided by the provincial office or the region, including the cost of administration and the central transport, based on the needs of each school individually, in line with the number of students and the school itself, to determine how to distribute the money to each of the [staff, devices, equipments and maintenance]. In this case, the Director is entrusted with the achievement of the objectives of the region through school. [2].

The Results

The application of the system of self-management in schools works on the needs of the pupils and the local community.

Application of self-management within the school contributes to improving the quality of education.

Application of self-management education contributes to strengthening self-monitoring on staff within schools.

Application of self-management achieving democratization.

Recommendations

Schools should apply the principle of self-management because of their benefits to students and community members.

Schools must apply self-management as it contributes to the strengthening of democracy.

Schools must apply the principle of self-management in schools because of its role in improving the quality of education.

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